

Serious Games as Research Instruments for Democratic Health Governance

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Abstract

Health systems increasingly face complex, value-laden challenges that require decisions to be effective and perceived as legitimate and inclusive. Existing consultation formats, however, often capture citizens' expressed preferences rather than the reasoning processes through which people reflect on ethical and political trade-offs. While deliberative mini-publics, citizens' assemblies, and participatory technology assessments have advanced democratic inclusion, they remain constrained by limited scalability, high organisational cost, and difficulty capturing interactional reasoning over time. Existing digital participation platforms, meanwhile, tend to elicit surface-level preference expression rather than structured deliberation. This paper examines the potential of serious simulation games as research instruments for examining and supporting democratic innovation in health governance. Building on insights from deliberative democracy, Science and Technology Studies, and empirical ethics, we outline a conceptual and methodological framework for a simulation game that invites participants to deliberate, decide, and justify policy choices within a dynamic health-system environment. The design enables the collection of quantitative, qualitative, and interactional data, allowing shifts in public reasoning to be traced through contemporary natural-language-processing techniques. Beyond data

generation, the game functions as a civic laboratory in which participants can engage with the practical tensions between efficiency, fairness, and legitimacy. We suggest that this dual empirical and participatory approach can provide new evidence on how democratic legitimacy is negotiated in practice and how ethical reflection might be integrated into the design of health governance.

Introduction

Health systems are increasingly confronted with complex and interdependent challenges – pandemics, resource scarcity, technological disruption, and widening inequalities – that force societies to negotiate difficult trade-offs among efficiency, fairness, and legitimacy (Daniels and Sabin 2008; WHO 2010; OECD 2023). Decisions about vaccine distribution, data sharing, or the prioritization of care are not merely technical; they are deeply ethical and political. While these debates are often framed as disputes over evidence, they are in fact conflicts over values – over what counts as fair, whose needs should be prioritized, and what risks are acceptable (Parkhurst 2016; Boswell 2022). Yet most participatory methods, such as surveys or consultation hearings, are ill-suited to capture how people reason about normative dilemmas. They tend to collect opinions as if they were stable data points, rather than tracing how citizens deliberate, revise their positions, and balance competing values under uncertainty. In rapidly changing environments, preferences evolve through learning and negotiation, not simple aggregation. This gap points to the need for participatory tools that can both engage the public in value-based reasoning and generate richer insights into how ethical and political judgments are formed in practice.

Recent research calls for “new approaches that specialize in imagining, experiencing and experimenting with futures” as part of governance transformations (Vervoort et al. 2022). This paper proposes a novel instrument for studying and fostering democratization in healthcare governance: a serious simulation game that recreates the decision environment of a public-health system under stress. Within this simulated polity, participants collectively confront evolving crises such as pandemics, budget shortages, or emerging technologies. Their task is not to “win” but to maintain a system that citizens perceive as both effective and legitimate.

The game functions as both a research laboratory and a deliberative arena. It allows researchers to collect empirical data on how participants reason, justify, and negotiate ethical trade-offs, while at the same time enabling participants to experience the tensions of real governance. The framework integrates insights from deliberative democracy (Dryzek 2002; Habermas 1996), empirical ethics (Ives et al. 2018; Molewijk et al. 2004), and STS analyses of hybrid forums (Callon et al. 2011). It treats play as a civic experiment, an embodied exploration of what democratized health governance might look like when diverse actors deliberate under constraint.

Here we develop a conceptual and methodological framework for such a game, outline the mechanics, and discuss implications for ethics, policy design, and participatory governance.

Background and rationale

Our approach builds on deliberative democracy, Science & Technology Studies (STS), and empirical ethics, taken together as a program for studying and improving public reasoning under uncertainty. In deliberative democracy, legitimacy flows from citizens and representatives exchanging reasons that others could reasonably accept (reciprocity) and publicly justifying decisions (accountability). Classic accounts anchor this ideal in communicative rationality and law, linking democratic legitimacy to the quality of public reasoning, while later work emphasizes moving from isolated forums to a “deliberative system” spanning mini-publics, media, movements, and institutions (Gutmann and Thompson 2000; Parkinson and Mansbridge 2012; Habermas 1996).

STS complements this by treating governance as “co-production”: facts, norms, and institutions are made together, so controversies are not only about evidence but also about social order. Technical democracy then calls for opening problem-framing, expertise, and design choices to affected publics, especially when stakes and uncertainties are high. This pushes us to include diverse knowers (experts, lay actors, marginalized groups) and to study how procedures shape what can be known and decided (Wynne 1998; Jasanoff 2004a; 2004b; Callon et al. 2011).

Empirical ethics provides the methodological bridge: it argues for integrating empirical data with normative analysis, clarifying when and how observations of real-world reasoning should inform ethical evaluation and institutional design (Salloch et al. 2015; Ives et al. 2018; Ives and Draper 2009). The “integrated empirical ethics” stream and the wider “empirical turn” in bioethics specify standards for combining data with theory without collapsing “is” into “ought”, a stance we adopt to study deliberation in practice while keeping normative criteria explicit (Molewijk et al. 2004; Molewijk 2004; Borry et al. 2005).

Situating our serious game instrument within these traditions allows us to operationalize deliberative principles at the system level; render co-production visible by embedding socio-technical assumptions into scenarios; and generate analyzable traces of public reasoning that feed back into normative assessment and design.

However, enabling deliberation at scale – and studying it rigorously – remains challenging. Here, serious games offer a form of “deliberative play”: they create a safe “magic circle” in which participants can experiment with decisions and arguments, mirroring a democratic forum but in a playful, consequence-free space (Gordon et al. 2017). Prior work has shown that role-playing games in civic settings can foster empathy and creativity; for example, a study using the @Stake game in New York City’s participatory budgeting process found that a role-play scenario led to more empathetic and novel ideas than a traditional Q&A format (Gordon et al. 2017). By encouraging players to assume perspectives of different stakeholders, games can spark social learning and creative problem-solving that might not emerge in conventional meetings (Gordon et al. 2017).

Why games for health governance research?

Serious games are particularly well-suited to health governance and ethics research for several reasons. Games can simulate complex, systemic interdependencies in ways that traditional surveys or interviews cannot. They function as dynamic models of society where policies, resources, and stakeholder actions interact. As Vervoort et al. note, games share many characteristics with scenario modeling and simulations – “including the simulation of existing and future systems and the exploration of future worlds and trajectories” – but are unique in allowing players to “explore new roles, new rules, and new interactions” within vivid, evolving scenarios (Vervoort et al. 2022). This means participants can experience the consequences of decisions in real time, revealing how changes ripple through a system (for instance, how a health policy decision might impact economic or social trust outcomes in the simulation). Complex concepts like feedback loops or long-term impacts become concrete through gameplay.

By leveraging the intrinsically motivating features of play, serious games tend to generate higher engagement than traditional methods. A systematic review by Hassan & Hamari found that gamified civic participation initiatives were consistently linked to increased citizen engagement, motivation, learning, and enjoyment (Hassan and Hamari 2020). Participants are more willing to invest time and effort when the activity is interactive and fun. In turn, this engagement leads to deeper learning: players often absorb complex information by doing (tackling challenges, weighing options) rather than passively listening. Prior studies in education and urban planning have demonstrated that game mechanics can spur collaboration, ideation, and the transfer of complex ideas into practice (Gordon et al. 2017). In health governance contexts, this means citizens can better grasp policy trade-offs and think creatively about solutions. For example, interactive role-play simulations for climate policy have been shown to significantly improve participants’ understanding of climate solutions and even increase their motivation to take real-world action (Rooney-Varga et al. 2025). Notably, these gains were sustained over months and observed across diverse sociodemographic groups, underscoring how game-based engagement can reach and benefit broad publics, not just the “usual suspects” of civic participation.

Serious games produce rich data on how people reason and where they stand on value-laden trade-offs. Unlike surveys that capture a single choice or opinion in isolation, a simulation game can record the full trajectory of a decision-making process – the proposals made, arguments exchanged, concessions negotiated, and justifications given for each action. This creates an empirical window into participants’ values and priorities. For instance, a player may initially prioritize economic efficiency, but when faced with a simulated pandemic in the game, might shift to prioritizing equity or public health, explaining their rationale as the crisis unfolds. These dynamic shifts are invaluable for researchers in democratic governance and ethics. They reflect “situated” moral and political reasoning, showing how abstract principles (fairness, liberty, safety, etc.) get applied or re-interpreted in context. Indeed, scholars in empirical ethics argue that purpose-built digital games can align with ethical

frameworks to investigate decision-making in context: such games “integrate context, narrative and embodiment in moral decision-making” and can yield “unique insights into normative and empirical issues” when rigorously designed (Pavarini et al. 2021). In other words, games can bridge the gap between normative theories (what people ought to value or do) and empirical observation (what people actually value or do when confronted with dilemmas). This makes them powerful instruments for fields like deliberative democracy and policy ethics, where understanding the interplay between ideals and practice is key.

The use of simulated or game-like exercises in governance is not without precedent. Policymakers and educators have long used role-play and scenario exercises to explore complex issues – for example, diplomatic “war-games” and crisis simulations have been staples in military and international relations training for decades (Vervoort et al. 2022). In recent years, we see an expansion of serious games into areas like urban planning, climate adaptation, and public health. A notable example is the World Climate simulation, a role-playing game of UN climate negotiations paired with a climate model; researchers found it increased participants’ knowledge, sense of urgency, and desire to act, even among those initially skeptical of climate science (Rooney-Varga et al. 2025). Similarly, in the domain of civic planning, games like @Stake and other participatory budgeting games have been piloted to involve citizens in generating ideas and allocating budgets (Gordon et al. 2017). These examples show that serious games can be designed to blend reflection, negotiation, and decision-making in a controlled environment, and that participants are capable of treating these games seriously – reflecting real-world behaviors – even as they remain games. Building on these successes, our framework formalizes the use of serious games specifically as research instruments: not only engaging participants but systematically capturing data to inform democratic governance theory and practice. To situate our proposed approach within existing methodological traditions, Table 1 compares different game- and simulation-based approaches and clarifies their relevance and limitations for studying democratic reasoning in health governance.

Approach	Characteristics	Typical Use Cases	Strengths	Limitations	Relevance to our research question
War games / crisis simulations	Strategic, time-pressured role-play to test decisions under uncertainty	Military, emergency preparedness, institutional stress-tests	Models high-stakes coordination and uncertainty	Prioritizes strategy over public deliberation; limited inclusion of lay perspectives	Useful for crisis dynamics; does not capture democratic justification/legitimacy (Vervoort et al. 2022).
Educational /	Serious games focused on	Medical/clinical training,	High engagement	Primarily didactic;	Shows complexity/system

training simulations	skill/knowledge acquisition	disaster drills, leadership courses	t, experiential learning	not designed for research-grade deliberation data	effects but rarely examines value trade-offs or reasoning (Gordon et al. 2017).
Policy simulation platforms	System-dynamics models with adjustable policy levers	Climate/economy models (e.g., World Climate/EnROADS)	Visualizes systemic consequences and feedbacks	Emphasizes outcomes over deliberation; thin justificatory traces	Clarifies trade-offs but lacks interactional/justificatory data (Rooney-Varga et al. 2025; Vervoort et al. 2022).
Participatory role-play civic games	Narrative scenarios for perspective-taking and co-creation	Urban planning, budgeting, environmental governance (e.g., @Stake)	Fosters empathy, social learning, idea generation	Data capture often limited; scalability issues	Supports perspective-taking but not systematically linked to theory-building (Gordon et al. 2017).
Gamified participation platforms	Points/badges/leaderboards for e-participation	Crowdsourcing ideas, civic reporting	Broad, low-barrier engagement	Captures preferences, not reasoning; risk of superficial input	Fails to capture justificatory processes crucial to legitimacy (Hassan and Hamari 2020).
Research-driven serious simulation games (proposed approach)	Dynamic governance simulation with deliberation, decisions, and justification logs	Democratic governance experimentation in health	Integrates behavior, discourse, and reasoning; analyzable multi-modal data	Requires careful co-design, ethics, and transparency	Directly studies legitimacy, value conflicts, and justificatory practices; bridges normative-empirical via recorded deliberation (Pavarini et al. 2021; Niemeyer et al. 2024).

Table 1. Comparison of game and simulation approaches used in policy and governance research, highlighting their methodological strengths and limitations for studying democratic legitimacy, value trade-offs, and deliberative reasoning in health systems.

Core concept of the game

The proposed simulation game functions as both an analytical instrument and a participatory experiment in democratic healthcare governance. Conceptually, it translates deliberative and co-productive ideals into an operational environment: a

dynamic model of a health system under stress, where diverse actors must deliberate, decide, and justify actions collectively. The game situates participants within a simulated public-health polity in which resources are finite, crises unfold unpredictably, and decisions carry ethical, political, and social consequences. By embedding uncertainty, asymmetries of information, and conflicting values into gameplay, it allows researchers to observe not merely what participants decide, but how they reason and justify their decisions under constraint.

Each session begins with a baseline configuration reflecting different governance archetypes, ranging from strongly centralized welfare systems to market-oriented or hybrid arrangements. Participants take on institutional roles (such as health minister, hospital director, patient advocate, insurer representative, trade union delegate, or community health organizer) not as caricatures but as structured perspectives that embody distinct responsibilities, constraints, and forms of power within the health system. These roles create vantage points through which participants explore how institutional mandates shape priorities, alliances, and conflicts.

Over successive rounds, the simulation begins with a vision-building phase in which participants collaboratively design the health and social care system they consider legitimate and desirable. Starting from shared principles rather than constraints, players define priorities such as universal access, family-work balance in caregiving, incentives for prevention, protections for vulnerable groups, or the role of public vs. private actors. This stage surfaces normative expectations and makes explicit what participants value before they encounter feasibility limits.

Only after this constructive phase do governance challenges emerge. These include both acute dilemmas (e.g. prioritizing access during a pandemic surge, responding to a data governance scandal that undermines trust) and long-term transformation pressures (e.g. designing fair remuneration for formal and informal caregivers, balancing investment between prevention and high-cost innovation, restructuring health financing in response to demographic change). As the simulation progresses, participants discover avoidable and unavoidable trade-offs that test the integrity of their initial principles. Rather than focusing solely on crisis or scarcity, the game is structured as a progressive negotiation between ideals and constraints, compelling participants to justify how their evolving decisions remain compatible with democratic legitimacy. Every scenario requires reasoning about competing values – including equity, efficiency, participation, reciprocity, and sustainability – and invites systematic reflection on what must be protected, compromised, or renegotiated to uphold a fair health system.

Decisions are organized across several interdependent domains: allocation of resources, regulation and restriction, technological adoption, and citizen engagement. Rather than evaluating outcomes through a single metric of success, the simulation traces evolving system indicators such as equity of access, legitimacy, trust, and resilience. These indicators are not conceived as “scores” but as feedback cues, prompting players to interpret the systemic implications of their actions and to adjust their governance strategies accordingly. The open-ended structure encourages

adaptive learning: players may reform decision rules, establish new participatory bodies, or redesign funding schemes as the game progresses, thereby performing institutional experimentation in miniature.

The epistemic function of the game lies in its ability to make public reasoning both visible and analyzable (Steenbergen et al. 2003; Niemeyer et al. 2024). Every deliberative exchange, negotiation, and justification is recorded, producing layered data: quantitative traces of decisions and outcomes; qualitative transcripts of deliberation; and interactional patterns revealing persuasion, coalition-building, or marginalization. This data offers a rare empirical window onto how ethical principles are interpreted and balanced in practice (Parthasarathy et al. 2019). It also exposes tensions between procedural ideals and situational pragmatism, showing how moral reasoning adapts when abstract commitments encounter scarcity and pressure.

From a normative perspective, the game enacts a democratizing logic, as it invites participants who might not otherwise share a decision-making space to engage in reciprocal justification within a shared frame (Abelson et al. 2003). In doing so, it operationalizes the concept of "technical democracy" (Farías and Blok 2016; Farías 2016) by transforming the site of governance into an experimental forum where expertise and experience cohabit. The process is not only informative but formative: participants experience first-hand the complexity of deliberation, potentially reshaping their understanding of legitimacy and accountability in health governance (Degeling et al. 2017).

By design, the simulation is flexible enough to accommodate different scales and contexts, while retaining a coherent theoretical structure. Its ultimate purpose is not prediction, but exploration: to generate empirically grounded insights into how people reason together about the common good in healthcare, and to test whether democratizing practices such as transparency, inclusivity, and shared justification can enhance both the perceived and actual legitimacy of decisions. In this sense, the game is a methodological bridge between normative theory and lived deliberation, turning the aspiration of participatory health governance into a tangible, researchable practice.

Game mechanics and data collection

Rather than presenting a fully specified tool, our aim in this paper is to outline a design space for research-driven serious games in democratic health governance. The mechanics described below are therefore illustrative options, grounded in deliberative theory, democratic innovation research, and empirical ethics. The final configuration of the simulation will be developed through iterative co-design and informed by empirical findings in future work, rather than predetermined at this stage.

A simulation-based approach enables the translation of abstract principles of deliberative governance into an interactive environment capable of generating empirical data. Rather than centering solely on crises or scarcity, each round may

unfold as a cycle of collective problem-solving, in which participants explore how a needs-based and democratically legitimate health and social care system could be organized. Scenarios can introduce evolving contextual information, such as shifting demographic needs, community care models, remuneration for formal and informal caregivers, or ethical questions linked to emerging technologies, alongside occasional stress conditions such as pandemics or resource shocks. Participants deliberate in real time, justify their proposals, and observe how different governance choices shape evolving outcomes. This structure mirrors real governance, where vision-building and institutional design are continuously negotiated under dynamic conditions.

At the interface level, one possible configuration includes a shared dashboard displaying indicators such as equity of access, service availability, workforce sustainability, public trust, or participation. A deliberation space (text or voice) records arguments, value conflicts, and coalition-building efforts. Decision menus enable policy proposals, procedural changes, and institutional reforms. Crucially, the emphasis is on justification rather than efficiency: actions require explicit reasoning, making deliberation and value articulation central components of gameplay rather than by-products.

From a research design perspective, the simulation functions as a configurable experimental environment. Researchers may vary initial system conditions, governance architectures, or procedural rules to examine how institutional design shapes public reasoning. For example, configurations may differ in terms of decision procedures (e.g. inclusive vs. delegated deliberation), accountability mechanisms (e.g. justification requirements), or participatory formats (e.g. advisory citizen input vs. fully co-decisional formats). Systematically varying these parameters enables both hypothesis testing and theory-building on deliberation, legitimacy, and ethical decision-making under institutional constraints.

To preserve pluralism and inclusion, the approach may integrate AI-supported stakeholder agents that represent institutional roles or underrepresented perspectives (e.g. caregivers' associations, disability rights advocates, future generations, rural community voices). These agents help ensure value diversity even in small groups, and their contributions are traceable alongside those of human participants.

This design space allows the generation of multi-layered datasets capturing both decisions and their justificatory foundations. Quantitative logs trace policy trajectories and system indicators over time. Qualitative transcripts of deliberation capture argument styles, appeals to fairness, and patterns of justification. Interactional data reveal participation asymmetries, persuasion dynamics, and coalition formation. Combined, these layers support a rich empirical analysis of democratic reasoning, consistent with integrated empirical ethics (Molewijk 2004; Ives and Draper 2009)

Rather than treating collective judgment as a black box, this approach renders visible the moral work of governance: how actors balance solidarity and autonomy, efficiency and equity, rights and responsibilities. The simulation thus serves not only as an engagement tool but as an experimental observatory of legitimacy in practice, capable

of illuminating how institutions might better align with democratic values over time. Design principles and implementation options are summarized in Table 2.

Design Principles (foundations)	Implementation Options (to be decided empirically/co-designed)
Deliberation centred on reason-giving and justification	Text vs. voice deliberation; synchronous vs. asynchronous rounds
Value pluralism and inclusion	Role-based play vs. open participant identity; human-only vs. AI-supported stakeholder agents
Dynamic governance environment (evolving scenarios)	Crisis scenarios vs. long-term transformation challenges; user-generated scenarios
Transparency of reasoning and decisions	Public justification logs; decision rationales stored or visualised
Reflexivity across rounds (learning over time)	Feedback dashboards; scenario debriefs; value tracking tools
Methodological integrity & empirical traceability	Logging of decision paths; argument tagging; deliberation coding
Ethical governance of participation	Informed consent; anonymity controls; deliberation safeguards
Co-design and iterative refinement	Participatory prototyping workshops; stakeholder advisory reviews

Table 2. Design principles and configurable implementation options for a research-driven serious game in democratic health governance.

Benefits, challenges, and mitigation strategies

Benefits

The serious-game-based research paradigm offers several compelling benefits for democratic governance.

By making participation interactive and game-like, we lower the barrier to entry for ordinary citizens to engage with complicated policy issues. People who might never attend a traditional public meeting might eagerly join a well-designed game session. Early evidence from related simulation efforts is promising: for example, the Climate Action Simulation game attracted over 350,000 participants worldwide, including many who do not typically engage in climate policy, and yielded sustained learning across ideological divides (Rooney-Varga et al. 2025). Serious games thus provide a pathway to broaden participation and give voice to more segments of society, making governance research more inclusive. Moreover, the enjoyable aspects of play can foster a sense of collective efficacy and motivation among participants – ideally seeding greater civic interest even beyond the game.

The game simulates the pressure-cooker environment in which real policy decisions occur, complete with limited resources, imperfect information, and crisis pressure. Participants therefore confront the same trade-offs decision-makers face (liberty vs. security, short vs. long-term benefits, etc.). Observing how they navigate these trade-offs provides practical insights for policy design. It can highlight which compromises the public finds acceptable and which they do not. For instance, we might learn that when forced to choose, most communities (in the game) favor legitimacy over efficiency – i.e. they would rather take slower, consensus-based decisions than fast unilateral ones – or vice versa. These insights can inform how we structure real-world decision processes. The simulation also helps identify policy options or institutional innovations that people invent during play (some of which may be unconventional yet effective). In a sense, each game session serves as a policy laboratory, generating ideas and exposing failure points. This is valuable for anticipatory governance: it's far better to discover in a game that, say, a certain emergency law causes public unrest, than to discover it the hard way in reality.

A key scholarly benefit is the blending of normative and empirical dimensions and approaches. Democratic governance research often struggles to reconcile philosophical ideals (what should be done) with empirical observations (what is done). Our game-based method allows a unique fusion: the game is built with normative principles in mind (e.g. elements of deliberative democracy, fairness criteria, rights of participation), yet it generates empirical data on how people actually behave within those structured norms. As Pavarini et al. argue, properly designed digital tools like games “align with theoretical frameworks in bioethics for empirical research” and can produce insights that advance both ethical theory and practice (Pavarini et al. 2021). In our context, this means the game can test democratic design principles: for example, theory might posit that including a citizen assembly increases legitimacy – the game lets us see if groups that implement a citizen assembly indeed fare better on legitimacy (trust, acceptance) indicators than those that don't. Conversely, empirical patterns from the game can challenge or refine theory: we might observe scenarios where highly inclusive processes paradoxically lead to worse outcomes, prompting questions about the limits of deliberation. Overall, this method bridges the empirical-normative gap, contributing to evidence-based democratic theory and ethically-informed practice.

Although the primary aim is research, an intentional side benefit is that participants learn and become more informed through the process. By grappling with realistic scenarios, players often come away with a deeper understanding of governance complexities and empathy for decision-makers and affected groups. This can be seen as a form of civic education or capacity-building. In trials of serious games in communities, researchers have noted increases in participants' sense of agency and understanding of policy issues (Gordon et al. 2017). Thus, even as we gather data from participants, we are also giving something back: an experience that can make citizens more prepared for real-world engagement. In the long run, widespread use of such games could foster a more deliberative democratic culture, where the public expects to weigh trade-offs and reason together (rather than just consume sound bites or express raw opinions).

Challenges, limitations, and mitigation strategies

Despite these benefits, we must also acknowledge significant limitations, challenges and risks in this approach as well as strategize on how to mitigate them.

Developing a high-fidelity health governance simulation game is technically challenging and potentially costly. It requires interdisciplinary expertise – game designers, domain experts, computer scientists, and social scientists – to collaborate. The simulation must strike a balance between complexity and usability: too simple, and it loses realism; too complex, and players become overwhelmed or the system becomes buggy. There are also infrastructure considerations (servers for online play, data security for storing interaction data, etc.). Funding and maintaining such a platform over time is non-trivial. We propose an iterative prototyping approach, starting with simplified scenarios and gradually adding complexity. Early versions could be played in a “paper prototype” or role-play format to test concepts with lower cost. In addition, leveraging open-source frameworks and partnerships can reduce development load. If successful, the value of the game as a research tool (and possibly as a public engagement platform) can justify sustained funding.

By design, any simulation is a reduction of reality. There is a concern that a game might oversimplify real-world dilemmas or omit critical factors, leading to misleading conclusions. Participants might treat the simulation’s constraints as gospel and not consider things the model left out. For instance, a game might not fully capture cultural or historical contexts that influence real governance, or might simplify human behavior into a few numeric indicators. To address this, we will involve subject-matter experts and diverse stakeholders in the co-design of the game scenarios – this helps ensure the scenarios are representative and salient. We will also keep players aware that this is a model, encouraging reflection on what was not captured and how that might affect decisions. From a research perspective, we will treat game findings as hypotheses or exploratory insights, rather than literal predictions. Triangulating with complementary methods (surveys, panels) will help check if patterns in the game might hold in real-world contexts. Finally, rigorous development and testing are crucial: if such tools are “developed and used with appropriate rigor”, they can indeed yield unique insights – implying that lack of rigor undermines their value (Pavarini et al. 2021). We will document assumptions in the game design (e.g., how we model public opinion or economic impacts) so that limitations are transparent.

Who plays the game is a critical question. If only policy specialists or a narrow demographic end up participating, the research insights will be correspondingly limited and possibly biased. Games, especially digital ones, might attract younger and more educated participants disproportionately, for example. There is also the issue of self-selection – those who choose to play might already be more civic-minded or cooperative, which could skew results (e.g., overestimating the public’s willingness to deliberate). This is where some complementary outreach is vital. Narrative data or surveys can capture input from thousands of people, including those less interested in games, and we can compare their profiles to game players to understand differences.

For the game sessions themselves, we will actively recruit for diversity, possibly through partnerships with civic organizations, schools, or community groups. Another idea is to incorporate the game into existing public consultation processes (some governments run youth councils or scenario workshops – the game could be a tool there, ensuring a built-in diverse audience). Additionally, to entice a broad range of participants, the game design should be accessible and rewarding: we can implement difficulty levels or support “observer” roles for those less inclined to actively play. By continuously monitoring the demographics of our participants, we can identify gaps (say, older citizens or minority groups underrepresented) and adjust our recruitment or adapt the platform (for instance, creating a facilitated analog version for communities with low computer access).

Perhaps the most subtle challenge is ensuring that the game itself does not encode a bias or promote a particular normative agenda unbeknownst to players. The selection of scenarios, the way options are framed, and the metrics of “success” all reflect value judgments by the designers. If, for example, the game implicitly always rewards consensus, it might nudge players toward a deliberative-democratic ideal that some political cultures might not share. Or if the crises chosen are skewed, the findings might overly emphasize certain values over others. Moreover, as game designers intervene in what is essentially a political exercise, they carry responsibility. As Vervoort et al. observe, when designers aim to support governance through games, they “inevitably enter political arenas and bear responsibility for understanding and managing their influence at the science-policy interface” (Vervoort et al. 2022). In short, the act of simulation is not neutral. To address normative bias, we are committed to a transparent and participatory design process. We involve a multidisciplinary advisory board – including ethicists, community representatives, and decision-makers – to review scenarios and game mechanics for balance and fairness. We explicitly incorporate multiple perspectives in scenario storytelling (for instance, each scenario brief might include statements from different stakeholder viewpoints, so the framing is not one-sided). The game will not enforce any single metric as “the” goal; instead, players see trade-offs across indicators and must form their own judgments about what a good outcome is. During analysis, we will be cautious to interpret results in context, acknowledging the value-framework of the game. In publishing results, we will discuss how the findings might differ if the game assumptions were changed, as a way to remain reflexive about our own influence. On the ethics front, we will ensure informed consent from participants, anonymization of data, and the ability to withdraw – treating the game much like a social experiment under ethical review.

In summary, while challenges like complexity, bias, and representativeness are non-trivial, we believe they can be managed through careful design and methodological pluralism. The mitigating strategies – expert co-design, iterative testing, multi-modal integration, and transparency – are built into our approach. By anticipating these challenges, we aim to harness the benefits of serious games for governance research while minimizing pitfalls. Challenges, limitations, and mitigation strategies are summarized in Table 3.

Challenge	Risk	Mitigation strategy
Technical complexity and cost	Prototype instability, high development burden, limited scalability	Iterative prototyping; start with low-fidelity role-play versions; modular build; open-source infrastructure; partnerships with civic tech/game studios
Model reduction / oversimplification	Loss of contextual realism; misleading conclusions	Co-design scenarios with domain experts and stakeholders; transparency about assumptions; reflexive debriefing; treat findings as exploratory
Participant representativeness	Biased samples; exclusion of marginalized groups; self-selection bias	Diversified recruitment; partnerships with communities; offline/analog access; demographic monitoring; comparison with survey baselines
Normative bias in design	Game encodes hidden values; promotes specific political outcomes	Independent ethics/advisory board; plural scenario framing; no single metric of "success"; explicit value transparency
Data ethics and consent	Privacy risks; unclear use of deliberation transcripts	Informed consent; data anonymization; secure storage; continuous ethics review
Gaming the system (strategic play)	Instrumental reasoning over genuine deliberation	Justification requirements; transparent rules; discourse quality indicators
Cognitive/interaction burden	Player fatigue; exclusion of less experienced participants	Accessible interface; structured facilitation; optional AI support agents; adaptive complexity
Misinterpretation of findings	Overclaiming causal policy effects	Mixed-method triangulation; publish model assumptions; avoid predictive claims; emphasize theory-building role

Table 3. Summary of methodological, practical, and ethical challenges in implementing serious games for democratic health governance, along with corresponding mitigation strategies to ensure rigor, inclusiveness, and normative transparency.

Conclusion

Serious simulation games offer a novel methodology for studying and advancing democratic governance in healthcare. By translating abstract ethical and policy dilemmas into lived, participatory experiences, they transform citizens from survey respondents into co-investigators of collective reasoning. Within such simulations, participants face the same constraints that real decision-makers do: limited resources, uncertainty, and competing values; and must negotiate solutions in conditions that

make the ethical and political nature of policy visible (Abelson et al. 2003; Degeling et al. 2017). In this sense, the game is not merely a tool for engagement but a research instrument that renders the dynamics of public reasoning observable and analyzable through recorded discourse and decisions (Steenbergen et al. 2003; Niemeyer et al. 2024).

Throughout this paper, we have outlined how a serious game could be designed to explore the democratization of healthcare governance. Drawing on deliberative democracy, Science and Technology Studies, and empirical ethics, the approach unites normative theory with empirical experimentation. Deliberative theory provides moral and procedural benchmarks for legitimate reasoning; STS emphasizes co-production and hybrid forums in which expertise and lay experience meet; and empirical ethics offers standards for linking observed reasoning to normative assessment without collapsing “is” into “ought” (Callon et al. 2011; Ives et al. 2018; Molewijk et al. 2004). Together, these strands allow researchers to study not just what people decide, but how they deliberate, justify, and learn under moral and institutional complexity.

The promise of this approach extends beyond producing new data. By engaging participants in structured deliberation about health policy, the simulation functions as a civic rehearsal of democracy itself, cultivating listening, reason-giving, and compromise. Evidence from role-play simulations and civic games indicates that such formats can deepen understanding, empathy, and motivation, including in contentious public-policy domains (Gordon et al. 2017; Rooney-Varga et al. 2025; Hassan and Hamari 2020). In that sense, the research method doubles as democratic capacity-building, blurring the line between studying democratic governance and enacting it.

Challenges remain, particularly in balancing realism with playability, ensuring inclusivity, and avoiding normative bias in scenario design. These are methodological problems that can be addressed through iterative co-design, transparency about modeling choices, and ethical oversight rooted in integrated empirical ethics (Ives et al. 2018; Molewijk et al. 2004). The potential rewards are considerable. Serious games enable the generation of thick empirical accounts of public reasoning under pressure and, at the same time, experimentation with more participatory and reflexive forms of health governance (Callon et al. 2011).

In an era when health systems must navigate both scientific uncertainty and social contestation, understanding how legitimacy is constructed through reasoning becomes essential. Serious simulation games provide a way to see democracy think: to observe, in real time, how people deliberate through crises and how institutions might better support that process, with analyzable traces that connect discourse quality and interaction patterns to outcomes (Steenbergen et al. 2003; Parthasarathy et al. 2019). As this approach matures, it promises not only to enrich the study of democratic governance but also to embody its values: inquiry and participation, reflection and reform, science and citizenship intertwined in the same experiment.

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